

LINGUI-POETICS OF THE RIDDLES

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Abstract

This article analyzes anthropocentric paradigm and the tendencies in the study of riddles in world linguistics, as well as the various opinions expressed in this regard. The views of Uzbek, Russian and English linguists on the lingui-poetics of the peoples oral work are discussed, riddles with metaphorical texts, aspects related to nationality in them are highlighted.

Key words

lingui-poetic, anthropocentric paradigm, riddle, metaphor, semantic, ethnolinguistic, morphological, syntactic, taboo.

After achievement of independence attention to our mother tongue has completely increased. As our president writes in his novel "Uzbekistan in the threshold of independence", "One who doesn't know his mother tongue, his ancestors, his root he is the one who doesn't have the future". Every language displays it's whole wealth and attraction, first of all, in people's oral work. People's oral work is considered as one of the most beautiful patters of the people's language which is full of metaphors.

Proverbs and riddles are real mirror of our language, lexical structure of Uzbek language, semantic features of the words and expressions are expressed in them. In the language of these genres are even used such kinds of words which are hardly used in current Uzbek literary language and dialects. Scientists interested the history of riddles during many years. This problem is to be learned widely by the Russian linguistics. V.P.Aneken found the origination of the riddles from fishermen's, hunters', cattle-raisers' secret speeches, taboos and strange talks. Scientists of English folklore Taylor, Green, Allen and others added of themselves corresponding portion to collecting and to be scientific research of English riddles. According to outstanding English scientist E.B. Taylor, riddle is not word-game of a present time which leads to unimportant traditional interactive joke; it is ancient

structure of task which requires serious reply. Sphinx's riddle might be it's typical sample.

As we aimed to study lingual-poetic features of people's riddles, we especially paid attention to the context features of the riddles. And we tried to investigate Uzbek and English riddles connecting them with the national mentality of the following peoples. Riddle is a text consisted of a distinctive, diminutive question stagnated in prosaic or poetry form of the quality of objects, like a figurative metaphoric expression and answer that should be found by the listener. According to the size feature of the expressed information in the text, we may include riddles to the minimal text type. According to the structure, riddles have poetry and prose forms. Riddles are so diminutive literarily, even they may consist of only two words. Nevertheless they consist of only two words, they express complete idea and meaning. According to the contextual features of the riddles, we divided riddles into metaphoric contextual riddles and classified contextual riddles. Metaphor is one of the poetic devices based on the similarity of this or that quality of the objects and events, which indicates essence of the traditional riddles. Riddles form metaphoric texts. Uzbek people's riddles mainly consist of metaphoric riddles. As we mentioned above, most of the riddles consist of metaphoric texts. But there are such kind of people's riddles they don't have metaphor. In such riddles classifying the quality or action of the being puzzled object dominates. We called such kind of riddles as classified textual riddles. Classified textual riddles are especially verb based riddles.

Riddles give some important materials to study lexical and grammatical value of the language besides they help to study some ethnographic sides of nations' financial-cultural life. In English people's folklore also riddles are important as ancient, popular, diminutive genre which expresses nation's life, social culture, traditions and literary-aesthetic sides of the.

According to the English scientist A.B. Taylor who collected English riddles and studied them scientifically, the riddle appeared in the culture history together with the proverb, it's prosperity corresponds to the low and middle periods of the civilization. As we mentioned above, the main part of Uzbek people's riddles consist of metaphoric textual riddles. You may come across with metaphoric textual riddles among English riddles.

For example:

There was a green house,

Inside the green house

There was a white house

Inside the white house there was a red house

Inside the red house there were lots of babies. (a watermelon)

But among English riddles classified textual type of riddles are much more efficient than metaphoric textual. Moreover in this type of riddles the given question is classified according to the object's action or quality by a being puzzled object.

I'm white, I'm round, but not always around. Sometimes you see me, sometimes you don't. What am I? (The Moon)

According to the structure English people's riddles have poetry and prose forms as well. But riddles in a prose form, which consist of a simple question, are much more productive. For example:

What goes round the house but never goes into the house? (The Sun)

Among English people's riddles there are a lot of riddles made up straightly in a question form. Riddles of this form are completely free of high artistic value, I mean artistry, and they straightly consist of question words. For example:

What teaches without talking? (a book)

Variation, which is very distinctive for people's oral heritage, is more widely used in riddles than in other folklore genres. Therefore many riddles have several variants. For example, riddles about rain have a lot of variants in Uzbek and English peoples' oral heritages.

In Uzbek folklore:

Мени сўрайдилар,

Кўринсам қочадилар (ёмғир)

In English folklore:

I am asked to come ,

I am waited for

But I make them hide

When I come (rain)

Thus, one of the people's oral creative work's the smallest genres is riddle which is artistically very diminutive type of folklore. All the times and in all nations riddles have been the a mean of developing the thought and a brain storming mean.

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